

FILE COMPRESSION SOFTWARE

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ABSTRACT

Compression is important because it helps reduce the consumption of expensive resources, such as disk space or connection bandwidth. However compression requires information processing power, which can also be expensive lossless type. The compressed data has to be decompressed before use. The decompression technique is just the reverse of compression. Use of the right compression tools yields more compact and loss-less data output.

The Domain “File Compressor” lets you reduce the overall number of bits and bytes in a file so it can be transmitted faster over slower Internet connections, or take up less space on a disk .Domain File compressor is a System Based Software.. It can use in the System as a utility. The type of compression we will use here is called lossless compression. The user need not depend on third party software’s like winzip, winrar, Stuff etc. the software can be used to compress files and they can be decompressed when the need arises

This research study aims to develop a system of improved facilities. The proposed system can overcome all the limitations of the existing system.

Key words: *File Compressor, compress, decompress, disk space*

INTRODUCTION

The aim of proposed system is to develop a system of improved facilities. The proposed system can overcome all the limitations of the existing system. The system provides data accuracy and save disc space. The existing system has several disadvantages and many more difficulties to work well. The proposed system tries to eliminate or reduce these difficulties up to some extent .The proposed system is file/folder compression or decompression based on the GZip algorithm. The proposed system will help the user to consume time. The proposed system helps the user to work user friendly and he can easily do the file compression process without time lagging. The system is very simple in design and to implement. The system requires very low system resources and the system will work in almost all configurations. It

has got following features Ensure data accuracy, minimize manual data entry, minimum time needed for the various processing, greater efficiency, better service.

Aim of the study

The aim of proposed system is to develop a system of improved facilities. The proposed system can overcome all the limitations of the existing system.

The system aims:

- To eliminate or reduce the difficulties of the existing system .
- To reduce the overall number of bits and bytes in a file.
- Files transmitted faster over slower Internet connections

LITERATURE REVIEW

Compression algorithm:

The deflation algorithm used by gzip (also zip and zlib) is a variation of LZ77 (Lempel-Ziv1977, see reference below). It finds duplicated strings in the input data. The second occurrence of a string is replaced by a pointer to the previous string, in the form of a pair (distance, length). Distances are limited to 32K bytes, and lengths are limited to 258 bytes. When a string does not occur anywhere in the previous 32K bytes, it is emitted as a sequence of literal bytes.(In this description, `string' must be taken as an arbitrary sequence of bytes, and is not restricted to printable characters.)

Literals or match lengths are compressed with one Huffman tree, and match distances are compressed with another tree. The trees are stored in a compact form at the start of each block. The blocks can have any size (except that the compressed data for one block must fit in available memory). A block is terminated when deflate() determines that it would be useful to start another block with fresh trees.

Duplicated strings are found using a hash table. All input strings of length 3 are inserted in the hash table. A hash index is computed for the next 3 bytes. If the hash chain for this index is not empty, all strings in the chain are compared with the current input string, and the longest match is selected. The algorithms for GZIP Decompression is the reverse process of GZIP compression.

The main algorithms are:

- GZIP algorithm

Here in this Domain we will use Gzip algorithm. Using C#.net we can import compression algorithmic classes directly e.g. using System.IO.Compression. The Domain File Compressor mainly include 3 modules

- Compress A File Or Folder

- De-Compress the file or folder

- Help

1. Compress file or folder

This module helps us to compress a file or folder. The compressed file will have a extension same as input . We can send the compressed file over the internet so that users having this software can decompress it.

2. Decompress a file or folder

This is the reverse process of file compression. Here we can decompress the compressed file and get the original file.

3. Help

File Compressor ,this is a software to convert your any file from normal file to compressed file.

Text file works best in compressing the data.

Steps to Compress a File:--

- 1.Name of the File after Compressing
- 2.Open the File to compress
- 3.Select the Path or Folder to Save the Compress File.
- 4.Press Compress Button To Convert the File.

Steps to Decompress the File:-----

- 1.Name of the File after DeCompressing
- 2.Open the Decompressed File.
- 3.Select the Path or Folder to Save the File.
- 4.Press DeCompress Button.

APPLICATION AREAS

The application areas of file compression are

- File storage
- Distributed systems.

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

In this project we created software to Compress/Decompress a file which contains the following modules.

1. Module (i)- Compress File
2. Module (ii)- Decompress File
3. Module (iii)- Help
4. Module (iv)- About Us
5. Module (v)- Exit

Module (i): Compress file or folder

This module helps us to compress a file or folder. The compressed file will have a extension same as input . We can send the compressed file over the internet so that users having this software can decompress it.

Fig .1-Compression/Decompression page

Here type the name of the file after compression then give the path of file to be compressed along with the file saving path.

Fig 2-compression path

Click on the compress button to compress the file. A message informing about successful compression of file will be displayed as a result.

Fig 3-compressed file

Module(ii): Decompress a file

This is the reverse process of file compression. Here we can decompress the compressed file and get the original file

Fig 4-Decompressed file

Module (iii):AboutUs

This module can have all the queries or comment related to the software and can know all about the file compressor software.

Fig 5-AboutUs page

Module (iv):Help

This module helps the user through steps of how to compress/decompress the required file. It explains step by step procedure to work with this software.

Fig 6-Help page

SYSTEM DESIGN

System Design is the most creative and challenging phase in the system life cycle. Design is the first step into the development phase for any engineered product or system. Design is a creative process. A good design is the key to effective system. System design is a solution how to approach the creation of a new system. System design transforms a logic representation of what is required to do into the physical specification. The specification is converted into physical reality during development.

LOGICAL DESIGN

The logical flow of a system and define the boundaries of a system. It includes the following steps:

- Reviews the current physical system – its data flows, file content, volumes ,frequencies etc.

- Prepares output specifications – that is, determines the format, content and frequency of reports.
- Prepares input specifications – format, content and most of the input functions.
- Prepares edit, security and control specifications.
- Specifies the implementation plan.
- Prepares a logical design walk through of the information flow, output, input, controls and implementation plan.
- Reviews benefits, costs, target dates and system constraints.

PHYSICAL DESIGN

Physical system produces the working systems by define the design specifications that tell the programmers exactly what the candidate system must do. It includes the following steps.

- Design the physical system.
- Specify input and output media.
- Design the database and specify backup procedures.
- Design physical information flow through the system and a physical design walk through.
- Plan system implementation.
- Prepare a conversion schedule and target date.
- Determine training procedures, courses and timetable.
- Devise a test and implementation plan and specify any new hardware/software.
- Update benefits , costs , conversion date and system constraints

Design/Specification activities

- Concept formulation.
- Problem understanding.
- High level requirements proposals.
- Feasibility study.
- Requirements engineering.
- Architectural design.

INPUT DESIGN

Input Design deals with what data should be given as input, how the data should be arranged or code, the dialog to guide the operating personnel in providing input, methods for preparing input validations and steps to follow when error occur. Input Design is the process of converting a user-oriented description of the input into a computer-based system. This design is important to avoid errors in the data input process and show the correct direction to the management for getting correct information from the computerized system. It is achieved by creating user friendly screens for the data entry to handle large volume of data. The goal of designing input is to make data entry easier and to be free from errors. The data entry screen is designed in such away that all the data manipulates can be performed. It also provides record viewing facilities. When the data is entered it will check for its validity. Data can be entered with the help of screens. Appropriate messages are provided as when needed so that the user will not be in maize of instant. Thus the objective of input design is to create an input layout that is easy to follow.

In this project, the input design consists of a log in screen, tab for compression/ decompression, source and destination browsing button, a menu list for selecting the algorithm, Compress/Decompress option, compress/decompress button.

OUTPUT DESIGN

A quality output is one, which meets the requirements of the end user and presents the information clearly. The objective of output design is to convey information about past activities ,current status or projections of the future, signal important events, opportunities, problems, or warnings, trigger an action, confirm an action etc. Efficient, intelligible output design should improve the system's relationship with the user and helps in decisions making. In output design the emphasis is on displaying the output on a CRT screen in a predefined format. The primary consideration in design of output is the information requirement and objectives of the end users .The major formation of the output is to convey the information and so its layout and design need a careful consideration.

There is a output display screen for showing the compressed/ decompressed file or folder details(Original file size, Compressed/Decompressed file size, Distinct characters).

RESULT ANALYSIS

System Study and Analysis

System analysis is a process of gathering and interpreting facts, diagnosing problems and the information to recommend improvements on the system. It is a problem solving activity that requires intensive communication between the system users and system developers. System analysis or study is an important phase of any system development process. The system is studied to the minutest detail and analyzed. The system analyst plays the role of the interrogator and dwells deep into the working of the present system. The system is viewed as a whole and the input to the system are identified. The outputs from the organizations are traced to the various processes. System analysis is concerned with becoming

aware of the problem, identifying the relevant and decisional variables, analyzing and synthesizing the various factors and determining an optimal or at least a satisfactory solution or program of action.

A detailed study of the process must be made by various techniques like interviews, questionnaires etc. The data collected by these sources must be scrutinized to arrive to a conclusion. The conclusion is an understanding of how the system functions. This system is called the existing system. Now the existing system is subjected to close study and problem areas are identified. The designer now functions as a problem solver and tries to sort out the difficulties that the enterprise faces. The solutions are given as proposals. The proposal is then weighed with the existing system analytically and the best one is selected. The proposal is presented to the user for an endorsement by the user. The proposal is reviewed on user request and suitable changes are made. This is loop that ends as soon as the user is satisfied with proposal.

Preliminary study is the process of gathering and interpreting facts, using the information for further studies on the system. Preliminary study is problem solving activity that requires intensive communication between the system users and system developers. It does various feasibility studies. In these studies a rough figure of the system activities can be obtained, from which the decision about the strategies to be followed for effective system study and analysis can be taken.

Here in the project File Compressor, a detailed study of existing system is carried along with all the steps in system analysis. An idea for creating a better project was carried and the next steps were followed.

FEASIBILITY STUDY

An important outcome of the preliminary investigation is the determination that the system requested is feasible. Feasibility study is carried out to select the best system that meets the performance requirements.

Feasibility study is both necessary and prudent to evaluate the feasibility of the project at the earliest possible time. It involves preliminary investigation of the project and examines whether the designed system will be useful to the organization. Months or years of effort, thousand for millions of money and untold professional embarrassment can be averted if an in-conceived system is recognized early in the definition phase.

The different types of feasibility are: Technical feasibility, Operational feasibility ,Economical feasibility.

1) Technical feasibility

Technical Feasibility deals with the hardware as well as software requirements. Technology is not a constraint to type system development. We have to find out whether the necessary technology, the proposed equipments have the capacity to hold the data, which is used in the project, should be checked to carryout this technical feasibility. The technical feasibility issues usually raised during the feasibility stage of investigation includes these

- This software is running in windows 2000 Operating System, which can be easily installed.
- The hardware required is Pentium based server.
- The system can be expanded.

2) Operational feasibility

This feasibility test asks if the system will work when it is developed and installed. Operational feasibility in this project:

- The proposed system offers greater level of user-friendliness.
- The proposed system produces best results and gives high performance. It can be implemented easily .So this project is operationally feasible.

3) Economical feasibility

Economical Feasibility deals about the economical impact faced by the organization to implement a new system. Financial benefits must equal or exceed the costs. The cost of conducting a full system, including software and hardware cost for the class of application being considered should be evaluated.

Economic Feasibility in this project:

- The cost to conduct a full system investigation is possible.
- There is no additional manpower requirement.
- There is no additional cost involved in maintaining the proposed system.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing system refers to the system that is being followed till now. The main disadvantage of this system is that the users depend on third party software's like winzip, winrar, Stuff etc.

The existing system requires more computational time, more manual calculations, and the complexity involved in Selection of features is high. The other disadvantages are lack of security of data, Deficiency of Data accuracy, Time consuming etc.

To avoid all these limitations and make the working more accurately the system needs to be computerized.

Draw backs of existing system.

- Lack of security of data.
- Deficiency of Data accuracy
- Time consuming.
- The users depend on third party software's like winzip, winrar, Stuff etc. To avoid all these limitations and make the working more accurately the system needs to be computerized

SYSTEM TESTING

Testing is a process of executing a program with the interest of finding an error. A good test is one that has high probability of finding the yet undiscovered error. Testing should systematically uncover different classes of errors in a minimum amount of time with a minimum amount of efforts.

Two classes of inputs are provided to test the process

1.A software configuration that includes a software requirement specification, a design specification and source code.

2.A software configuration that includes a test plan and procedure, any testing tool and test cases and their expected results.

Testing is divided into several distinct operations:

1. Unit Testing

Unit test comprises of a set tests performed by an individual program prior to the integration of the unit into large system. A program unit is usually the smallest free functioning part of the whole system. Module unit testing should be as exhaustive as possible to ensure that each representation handled by each module has been tested. All the units that makeup the system must be tested independently to ensure that they work as required .During unit testing some errors were raised and all of them were rectified and handled well. The result was quiet satisfactory and it worked well.

2. Integration Testing

Integration testing is a system technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. The objective is to take unit tested modules and build a program structure that has been dictated by design. Bottom 28up integration is the traditional strategy used to integrate the components of a software system into functioning whole. Bottom-up integration consists of unit test followed by testing of the entire system. A sub-system consists of several modules that communicated with other defined interface.

The system was done the integration testing. All the modules were tested for their compatibility with other modules .They test was almost successful. All the modules coexisted very well, with almost no bugs. All the modules were encapsulated very well so as to not hamper the execution of other modules.

3. Validation Testing

After validation testing, software is completely assembled as a package, interfacing errors that have been uncovered and corrected and the final series of software test; the validation test begins. Steps taken during software design and testing can greatly improve the probability of successful integration in the larger system. System testing is actually a series of different tests whose primary purpose is to fully exercise the compute –based system.

4. Recovery Testing

It is a system that forces the software to fail in a variety of ways and verifies that the recovery is properly performed.

5. Security Testing

It attempts to verify that protection mechanisms built into a system will in fact protect it from improper penetration. The system's security must of course be tested from in vulnerability form frontal attack.

6. Stress Testing

Stress tools are designed to confront programs with abnormal situations. Stress testing executes a system in a manner that demands resources in abnormal quantity and volume.

7. Black Box Testing

Black box testing is done to find out the following information as shown in below :

- 1.Incorrect or missing functions.
- 2.Interface errors.
- 3.Errors or database access.
- 4.Performance error.
- 5.Termination error.

The mentioned testing is carried out successfully for this application according to the user's requirement specification.

8. Test Data Output

After preparing test data, the system under study is tested using the test data. While testing the system using test data, errors are again uncovered and corrected by using above testing and corrections are also noted for future use.

MAINTENANCE

Maintenance is the tail end of life cycle but it is the most expensive and consumes energy, cost and time in the long run.

After a new system has been implemented, problems and errors and discrepancies appear and must be fixed. This required "system maintenance" as an ongoing process.

When the system maintenance becomes more costly and time demanding, new system will have to be thought of, thereby completing the full system life cycle.

Fig 7- software maintenance

IMPLEMENTATION

Operational systems are quickly taken for granted. Every system requires periodic evaluation after implementation. A post-implementation review measures the system’s performance against predefined requirements. Unlike testing, which determines the system failures so that the necessary adjustments can be made; a post-implementation review determines how well the system continues to meet performance specifications.

A post-implementation review is an evaluation of a system in terms of the extent to which the system accomplishes stated objectives and actual projects costs exceed initial estimates.

The review team prepares a formal review plan around the objective(s) of the review, the type of evaluation to be carried out, and the time schedule required. An overall plan covers the following areas:

- 1.Administrative plan – Reviews area objectives, operating costs, actual operation performance, and benefits.
- 2.Personnel requirements plan – Reviews performance objective and training performance to date.
- 3.Hardware Plan – Reviews performance specifications.
- 4.Documentation review plan – Reviews the system development effort

CONCLUSION

The project File Compressor is completed, satisfying the required design specifications. The system provides a user-friendly interface. The software is developed with modular approach. All modules in the system have been tested with valid data and invalid data and everything work successfully. Thus the system has fulfilled all the objectives identified and is able to replace the existing system. The constraints

are met and overcome successfully. The system is designed as like it was decided in the design phase. The system is very user friendly and will reduce time consumption. This software has a user-friendly screen that enables the user to use without any inconvenience. The user need not depend on third party software's like winzip, winrar, Stuff etc. The software can be used to compress files and they can be decompressed when the need arises .The application has been tested with live data and has provided a successful result. Hence the software has proved to work efficiently.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The different areas where we can use this application are:

- While it works in both public and private sectors, it is particularly focused on combating time and enhance the speed.
- Its scope includes in internet speed enhancement
- Through the use of this, it seeks to accountable to the people, and to promote efficiency and frugality.
- It also gives wide interpretation to “gratification other than remuneration” and “misconduct”.
- Thus, it is not necessary to prove that a public servant actually sought a bribe in cash, or was actually given. It is enough to show that undue favour or disfavour or undue service or disservice were given or sought to be given.
- The objective of this research study is to serve as a common men’s ground for locally and globally.

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